

EXPRESSION OF CONJUNCTIVE STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS THROUGH REPETITION

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Abstract. *This article provides an overview of how repetition is used to express conjunctive structural elements in German language, illustrating its importance in enhancing coherence and clarity in communication.*

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In German language, conjunctive structural elements play a pivotal role in linking various parts of a sentence or text, facilitating coherence and conveying logical relationships. An intriguing aspect of expressing these elements involves the use of repetition, which serves to emphasize, reinforce, or contrast ideas. In this article, we explore how repetition functions as a powerful tool for expressing conjunctive structural elements in German, enhancing clarity and effectiveness in communication.

The use of conjunctive structural elements, such as conjunctions, plays a crucial role in connecting different parts of a sentence or text in German. However, in addition to their conventional function, repetition serves as a powerful mechanism for emphasizing and reinforcing these elements. In this article, we will explore how repetition is employed to express conjunctive structural elements in German language, thereby enhancing coherence and clarity in communication.

One notable function of repetition is its use for emphasis. By repeating conjunctive elements within a sentence or across sentences, speakers or writers draw attention to the relationships between clauses or ideas, amplifying their significance. For example:

"Ich mag Kaffee, und meine Schwester mag auch Kaffee." (I like coffee, and my sister also likes coffee.)

"Er kam, weil er helfen wollte. Er kam, weil er gebraucht wurde." (He came because he wanted to help. He came because he was needed.)

Repetition for emphasis is a linguistic technique used to highlight the importance or significance of certain elements within a sentence or text. In the context of conjunctive structural elements in German language, repetition can serve to amplify the connection between clauses or ideas, drawing attention to their logical relationship. Here are some examples illustrating how repetition is employed for emphasis:

1. Repeating conjunctions within a sentence:

Sie mag Kaffee, und er mag auch Kaffee." (She likes coffee, and he also likes coffee.)

"Er kam, weil er helfen wollte. Er kam, weil er gebraucht wurde." (He came because he wanted to help. He came because he was needed.)

2. Repeating conjunctions across sentences:

"Entweder gehen wir ins Kino oder wir bleiben zu Hause. Oder wir treffen uns mit Freunden." (Either we go to the cinema or we stay at home. Or we meet with friends.)

In these examples, the repetition of conjunctions such as *"und"* (*and*) and *"oder"* (*or*) serves to emphasize the connection between clauses or choices presented in the text. By repeating these conjunctions, speakers or writers underscore the importance of the relationships they convey, ensuring that the reader or listener recognizes their significance.

Repetition for emphasis can enhance clarity and coherence in communication, making it easier for the audience to grasp the intended message or logical progression of ideas. In the context of conjunctive structural elements in German, this technique contributes to the effectiveness of linguistic expression by highlighting key connections and relationships within the text.

Parallel structure, also known as parallelism, involves the repetition of similar grammatical structures or patterns within a sentence or across sentences. In the context of conjunctive structural elements in German language, parallel structure can be employed to create symmetry and coherence, enhancing the flow of the text and clarifying relationships between ideas. Here are examples illustrating how parallel structure is utilized:

1. Repeating similar constructions within a sentence:

"Entweder gehen wir ins Kino oder wir bleiben zu Hause." (*Either we go to the cinema or we stay at home.*)

"Sowohl Maria als auch Peter mögen Fußball." (*Both Maria and Peter like soccer.*)

2. Repeating similar constructions across sentences:

"Sie mag Kaffee, und er trinkt Tee. Sie liebt das Meer, und er bevorzugt die Berge." (*She likes coffee, and he drinks tea. She loves the sea, and he prefers the mountains.*)

In these examples, parallel structure is evident in the repetition of similar grammatical patterns, such as the use of coordinating conjunctions (*"entweder...oder"* - *"either...or"*, *"sowohl...als auch"* - *"both...and"*) and the mirroring of sentence structures. This repetition creates a sense of balance and harmony in the text, making it easier for the audience to follow the logical progression of ideas.

Parallel structure enhances clarity and coherence in communication by organizing information in a systematic and structured manner. In the context of conjunctive structural elements in German, employing parallel structure contributes to the effectiveness of linguistic expression by reinforcing connections between ideas and facilitating comprehension for the audience.

Repetition for contrast is a linguistic technique used to emphasize differences or contradictions between ideas or elements within a sentence or text. In the context of conjunctive structural elements in German language, repetition can be employed to highlight contrasting relationships between clauses or choices presented in the text. Here are examples illustrating how repetition is used for contrast:

1. Repeating contrasting conjunctions within a sentence:

Sie mag Kaffee, aber ich trinke lieber Tee." (*She likes coffee, but I prefer tea.*)

Er ist nicht nur intelligent, sondern auch fleißig." (*He is not only intelligent, but also hardworking.*)

2. Repeating contrasting conjunctions across sentences:

"Sie wollte ins Kino gehen. Er hingegen wollte zu Hause bleiben." (*She wanted to go to the cinema. He, on the other hand, wanted to stay at home.*)

"Sie arbeitet im Büro, während er draußen im Garten arbeitet." (*She works in the office, while he works outside in the garden.*)

In these examples, the repetition of contrasting conjunctions such as *"aber"* (*but*), *"sondern"* (*but rather*), *"nicht nur...sondern auch"* (*not only...but also*), and *"während"* (*while*) serves to emphasize the differences or contradictions between the ideas or actions presented. By repeating these conjunctions, speakers or writers highlight the contrasting relationships, ensuring that the reader or listener recognizes the differences between the elements being compared.

Repetition for contrast enhances clarity and emphasis in communication by drawing attention to the distinctions between ideas or elements. In the context of conjunctive structural elements in German, employing repetition for contrast contributes to the effectiveness of linguistic expression by emphasizing the divergent relationships between clauses or choices presented in the text.

Repetition emerges as a potent mechanism for expressing conjunctive structural elements in German language. Through strategic repetition, speakers and writers can underscore relationships, create parallel structures, or highlight contrasts, thereby enhancing coherence and clarity in communication. By leveraging repetition effectively, communicators can elevate the impact and effectiveness of their expressions in German.

In conclusion, the use of repetition as a linguistic device in conjunction with conjunctive structural elements significantly enhances clarity, coherence, and emphasis in German language communication. Throughout this exploration, we have seen how repetition serves various functions, including emphasis, parallelism, and contrast, thereby reinforcing the relationships between clauses or ideas and facilitating comprehension for the audience.

By strategically employing repetition within sentences or across sentences, speakers or writers can effectively highlight the significance of certain elements, create symmetry and coherence in the text, and emphasize differences or contradictions between ideas. This enhances the overall effectiveness of linguistic expression in German, making it easier for the audience to follow the logical progression of ideas and grasp the intended message.

In essence, repetition plays a crucial role in expressing conjunctive structural elements in German language communication, contributing to the construction of coherent and impactful texts. Through its use, communicators can elevate the clarity, coherence, and emphasis of their expressions, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of communication in German language contexts.

REFERENCES

1. Grundstufen-Grammatik für Deutsch als Fremdsprache: Erklärungen und Übungen by Monika Reimann
2. Gjanyans E.M., Astanova G.M., Astapova G.M. Сравнительно-сопоставительный анализ повтора в парцелированных структурах английского и русского языков. Collection: Semantic-stylistic studies of text and sentences. Leningrad, 1980. 31-38 p.
3. Guliga E.B. Теория сложноподчиненного предложения в современном немецком языке. –Moscow., 1971. 206 p.